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COLLECTIVE INTELIGENCE IN ROBOTICS LABS: MAPPING THE FLOWS OF INFORMATION

M. Braga¹

CEFET/RJ Federal Center for Technological Education
Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

C. Schettini

CEFET/RJ Federal Center for Technological Education/Militar School
Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

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ABSTRACT

Knowledge is the feedstock that students work with in STEM learning environments (labs of basic sciences, robotics labs, makerspaces, etc). When students are developing projects in these environments a huge quantity of knowledge is being spread, information is being stored in both people and devices, and a collective intelligence is also being created. The STEM environments should be spaces where the knowledge can flow easily among each one of these sources. However, there are many factors that can create bottlenecks for these streams. These flows and bottlenecks must be mapped by knowledge managers (teachers, mentors, etc) during the activities, aiming to improve its spread. The research from this case study in a robotics workshop aims to create ways to study and knowledge management in STEM environments. In this target, a group of students from different classes were gathered in a robotics lab for an introductory activity. The structure of the activity was an initial contact with robotics focused on learning both the programming and assembly of robots as well as the phases of development in an engineering project. All activities were recorded with cameras positioned in different points. The exchange of information was registered and inserted in software of Social Networks Analysis. The map allowed understanding in some features of the information flows established by the students. From this map it is possible to change the environment setting to improve these flows. This research can help to understand and change different configurations of all engineering education environments by improving their knowledge management.

¹ M. Braga
marcobraga@namelab.education

1 INTRODUCTION

The STEM learning environments are not static spaces. When students are working on an engineering project, knowledge is built through various flows of information that fill the entire space. The work in a robotics learning lab, for example, is naturally collaborative and complex. There is always interaction among students, between students and the professor, or between students and devices and or tools. Therefore, the interaction (learning) can happen among humans directly or between humans and artifacts, because the students acquire knowledge manipulating artifacts as robotics pieces, engines and software.

The knowledge flows can have different configurations depending on several factors like architecture of the lab, position of workbenches, and distribution of kits and tools. The mapping of these flows can furnish important information to improve the spread of knowledge in these environments.

The mapping of these flows can show the interactions among students, teacher, and artifacts. The intention of this work is to identify these good pathways and bottlenecks aiming to improve the knowledge management in these STEM environments. The results can stimulate the emergence of a collective intelligence among the students and aide in the creation of innovative environments for engineering project developments in schools and universities.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORKS

This research is founded with the view that work in a STEM environment can be understood as being a network, where several actors (vertices in the language of graphs) play important roles in the exchange of information and by consequence in the learning. Two theories will be highlighted here that can contribute to the understanding of knowledge management in STEM environments, specifically in robotics labs: The Actor-Network Theory (ANT) and The Collective Intelligence.

2.1 The Actor-Network Theory

The actor-network theory emerged as a response to traditional sociological studies, where social relations were studied only among people. For the advocates of actor-network theory several artifacts play an important role in the social relationship that cannot be overlooked in these studies [1] [2]. In the modern world, the technological artifacts are not only mediators between humans; they also have the power to change these relationships. Verbeek [3] cites the example of the introduction of the microwave oven in American households in the final decades of twentieth century. In past times, dinner was a moment of conversation (information exchange) between members of families. Everyone sat at the table and talked about the day's events in both work, and community; however with the advent of frozen food and the microwave oven, many families did not eat at the same time as heating the dishes was not done at the same time. The diffusion of information in the communities has changed. The

microwave began to play a preponderant role in the social relationships of the communities. It has created a bottleneck in the dissemination of information from the community social network. This has also occurred with the massification of the use of smartphones. People stay constantly connected to their social network through cyberspace and far from people physically around them.

When students begin to develop projects in the Robotics Lab, they become part of a knowledge network. Their learning comes from several sources. Teacher and classmates take part of a small network inside the robotics lab, although this network can be enlarged by the use of smartphones that connected the students to other similar experiences through the internet. Today You tube is the most important source of information for students involved in engineering projects.

Each actor of this network should have a free connection with everyone else. This is the ideal condition for the spread the knowledge in the network. But we know that it not happen for several reasons. This is the goal of knowledge management in the STEM labs, identify the bottlenecks to eliminate its.

2.2 Collective Intelligence

Depending on the project, the students will need to seek information from different sources that have already researched that topic. This learning process is fundamental, because the first step is to gather information from knowledge storages where other networks have already deposited their projects (You tube, websites, visits of campus companies, etc). This first step connects them to several other networks who are working or have already worked with the same problem. At the end of the work, it is important that each team posts on internet their process and the final product. This kind of collaboration allows them to make their contribution so that this network can be expanded. This kind of collaboration is similar to the bazaar method of software development [4]. It allows for the emergence of collective intelligence (people working in collaboration, but not synchronically) and a collaborative intelligence (people working synchronically). In the robotics lab, the students can keep collaboration synchronically, each one of them exchanging knowledge with others.

Levy [5] wrote about the cyberculture and networks, developing the concept of Collective Intelligence (CI). For him, the knowledge is spread among several people and several data-bases. The intelligence is a function of coordinated work among people and between people and sources of knowledge. Because of this, people should count on different ways of connecting and several sources of knowledge storage in places with easy access. The great intellectual centers of Antiquity like Bagdad and Alexandria or in the Middle Age produced a good team of thinkers and large libraries.

The Collective Intelligence does not emerge naturally. It is fundamental to create a proper environment where people can work together focusing on the goals and

sharing knowledge. The elements of the team should have complementary skills and competencies.

When teachers create teams for collaborative learning, it is not easy to preview what kind of collective intelligence will emerge from that activity. They can create a proper space in the STEM environment but what is going to happen from that point cannot be foreseen.

From a case study, we intend to understand some of the characteristics of a collaborative learning strategy and how the students learn to work in engineering projects. A network should emerge from a dynamic where the teacher, the students and several devices become actors of a process where knowledge may flow freely among all of them.

3 METHODS & RESEARCH DESIGN

The first challenge of this research is to understand how the students build their own processes of information exchange during the development of an engineering project. In the first moment, this construction is almost random. There are several factors that give shape to this process. The first of them is the design of the environment. The position of workbenches or the place where the tools and robot kits are stored can draw the first topology of network. The pedagogy used in the activity can create different ways of knowledge flows too. The students can be stimulated to stay at the workbenches interacting with their team or circulating through in the environment and interacting with several elements such as tools, devices, and other teams. Each one of these elements can be set up previously to enhance the flows of information. The set up established by the students during the activity should be studied by the teachers to understand what should be changed. From this first set up, it is possible to change the position of non-human actors (furniture, architecture, etc.) or the pedagogies, creating a new topology aiming to improve the flow of information. It is necessary to create a research methodology that allows to map the paths of where the information is traveling. For this, we will use the methodology of video analysis and tools of social network analysis. We can think of the interaction among teacher, students and artifacts as a knowledge network where information is being exchanged all of the time.

This workshop was proposed to students from middle and high school (7th, 8th and 9th grades). The goal was to introduce them to engineering work through a robotics introductory project. They needed to assemble a car and coding it for a lap in a circuit.

After the presentation of the proposal, 21 students enrolled in the workshop. However, only 16 students attended all work meetings. Each one received a number of ID. They could choose their team freely. For this reason, the number of students on each team is not the same.

The students chose their position in the workbenches according to their preferences (Fig 1). The teacher did not indicate positions.

The topology analyzed here was built in one of the first days of the activity. This activity was recorded on video for analysis [6]. Two cameras were used for recording the interactions of actors. The researchers watched the videos and noted the interaction for twenty minutes. They noted the number of interactions creating a spreadsheet. This data was inserted in the Gephi software which created the map of interactions.

This work is the first analysis of these interactions. The goal is to detect the creation of a Collective intelligence through the measurement of clustering coefficient in the network created by the lab.

The duration of the workshop was 4 months. The twenty minutes of observation was the first proof point. All other work meetings were accompanied by a researcher and were recorded in a field diary.

4 RESULTS

The first observation was the position chosen by the students for organization of the work. The teams chose workbenches near the teacher. The teacher is the reference in the traditional learning environments, but after the work started all the spaces were occupied.

Fig. 1. Initial Lab Configuration

In the traditional lab each team worked from their workbenches with a great interaction among the students of the same team. However, the set-up of the environment blocked the interaction between teams. Braga and Guttman [7] argued that when there is a common place in the STEM environments to take tools or general materials, the collaboration grows and there is higher interaction among all students. The teacher put a general workbench in the center of the

environment with tools and pieces of the robotics kit to perform the role of a contact point among students. The intention was to promote the collaboration through the sharing of tools and robotic kit pieces. Each student could pick up a tool on the workbench and after using it would return it to the initial place so that other teams could use it too. This movement would induce the exchange of information at the workbench.

However, after removing tools from the central workbench, the students left it on the workbench of their own team. This situation created a new role for these tools and robotics pieces. The movement of students became more intense. They needed to pick up the tools from the workbenches of other teams. The tools and robotic pieces played a role of pollination of knowledge, because they allowed the students to move around the environment. They could see the work of classmates and suggest improvements or collect good ideas. The teacher or mentor could perform this role too, because the consults from them produced movement in the environment.

Fig. 2. – The network created during the initial activity. CC = 0,358

The network built in the Lab has 17 human actors (vertices), with 16 students and the teacher (P). The workbench with tools and robotics pieces is the non-human actor (R), making a total of 18 actors. The Collective Intelligence is built from the interaction of all these actors. Students sometimes need to interact with the teacher, and also with the tools and robotic pieces. When they choose a tool or a piece, they were thinking about the future actions and the basic needs to complete the task in their minds. Consequently, they are learning engineering.

In the ideal condition of interaction for the building a Collective Intelligence, each actor should interact with the other 17 actors. However, this did not happen, total interactions were not completed.

The Clustering Coefficient (CC) is the relationship between the real interactions (RIT), that is the interactions that really existed, and the total of possible interactions (TPI)[7].

$$CC = \frac{RIT}{TPI} = 0,358 \tag{1}$$

The data collected from the network indicates that only 35,8% of possible interactions happened. This number would be a good clustering coefficient for a network with a big number of actors. But for a small network it is not good.

The situation could have been more critical if the teacher and the workbench were excluded from the network.

Fig. 3. The interaction without the teacher (P) and the robotics pieces workbench (R).

In this case, the clustering coefficient goes down to $CC = 0,2$.

Only 20% of possibilities of interactions took place in this network. It is not a good value for a small network.

5 DATA ANALYSIS

Some problems can be solved before the next activities in this environment with the improvement of interactions and to creating a more robust Collective Intelligence.

- a) The teacher kept the centrality of the process. The activity is not a traditional class, but the teacher worked as a mentor for all students. All students-maintained interaction with the teacher, even those that were isolated from the other ones, like 7, 14 19.
- b) The development of projects in workbenches can induce the students to work only inside their teams. Students 7, 14 and 19 stayed connected only with classmates of their own team. It can be a personal issue or a question of environment setup. They were in the points of lab that didn't allow great movements or easy interaction with other classmates. Other configurations of lab should be tested.
- c) Students 1, 2 and 9 had the most connections with everyone. However, the big hub of this process was student 1. Student 9 had connections with students 5, 17, 20, 12 and 2, but four of them were on their own team. Only the student 2 was outside. Student 2 kept interactions with classmates 1, 5, 9, 11, 15, and 17, but 2 students were from their own team and the others came from only 2 other teams. Student 1 kept connections with classmates 2, 6, 8, 12, 14, 16, 20, 21. There are students in these connections from all teams. He is the hub of the network. This is an important issue for knowledge management because the hubs of knowledge networks are great information diffusers. Almost all information travelled through this hub. If the teacher needs to share relevant information with the teams, it important to know the pathway to implement this quickly.
- d) Even the isolated students 7, 14 and 19 are so close to student 1. Student 14 is directly linked because they worked on the same team. Student 7 had the intermediation of student 6 and student 19 was linked through student 8.
- e) Students 1 and 2 started the project in distant places in the lab. The central workbench had an important role in the connection between them. If this connection were blocked during the activity, we would break the network into two clusters with fewer connections between them. Therefore, the interaction between these two students was very important to spread information.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Other studies like this one should be repeated with other configurations of the lab. We used a traditional setup of the lab, with workbenches separated by teams. The number of workbenches was bigger than the number of students. Much of this space could have been used as a circulation area. Students 7 and 19 wouldn't

have remained trapped between the benches. Student 14 seemed blocked by student 21 in the beginning of the activity however it didn't remain that way because student 21 circulated through the environment.

The best configuration would have been where the workbenches stayed in the center of the environment, without a part pull over the wall. It would have been necessary for each team to work on the workbench, but each student could have the capacity to circulate around it.

The central workbench with tools and robotic pieces played its role with efficiency. It produced the meeting of many students and the exchange of information.

The teacher also performed his function as a mentor. He attended the student requests and oriented them with solution for many problems.

This methodology is being used by us as a tool for knowledge management in the development of engineering projects, both in the pre-university engineering education and in undergraduate courses. The next step will be the introduction of concepts of knowledge management in engineering education from these results from this methodology. It will be necessary that they learn to manage their work to improve their Collective Intelligence in the development of projects.

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